

Instrument

INTRODUCTION

Dear professor, I am a researcher who is concerned about research in our alma mater and taking into account that it is convenient to obtain scientific evidence that allows improving scientific production, I am proposing to carry out the study: “:Factors associated with scientific production of professors working at a private university in Peru”.Whose authorization from the ethics committee is No. 158-2020 of the UPNW.

Your participation in this study is completely voluntary and you may choose not to participate. If you decide to participate in this research, you may withdraw from it at any time. If you decide not to participate or if you decide to withdraw from the study, you will not be penalized in any way. The procedures for this study include completing an online questionnaire that will take about 35 minutes. All your answers will be confidential.

All information collected will be stored in password-protected electronic format. To help preserve confidentiality, the data for analysis will not contain any information that personally identifies you. The anonymized information may be shared only among the research team and will be used only for academic purposes that will allow proposing strategies that encourage the creation and dissemination of research in universities.

If you have any questions about this study, please contact Dr. Oriana. Rivera Lozada to email:oriana.rivera@uwiener.edu.pe

ELECTRONIC CONSENT: Please choose the option you prefer below.

By clicking the "I consent" button, you indicate that:

- you have read the information above,
- you are 18 years of age or older,
- has voluntarily agreed to participate, and
- You have agreed to be contacted if you have provided the appropriate information.

If you do not want to participate in this study, please decline your participation by clicking the "I do not give my consent" button.

I give my consent:

I do not give my consent:

PERSONAL FACTORS

1. Gender: Feminine Male
2. Date of Birth: ____/ ____/ ____
Day month Year
3. Age: _____ in completed years
4. Marital status:
Single cohabitant Married Widower Divorced
5. Number of children: _____
6. Profession: _____
7. Years of professional practice: _____
8. Years of teaching practice: _____
9. Number of institutions where you work: _____
10. Are you currently registered in the National Directory of Researchers (DINA) of CONCYTEC?
Yes NO
11. Are you currently Recognized by the National Registry of Researchers (RENACYT) of CONCYTEC?
Yes NO
12. Yes, your answer is affirmative in which category:
Maria Rostworowski III
Maria Rostworowski II
Maria Rostworowski I
Carlos Monge IV
Carlos Monge III
Carlos Monge II
Carlos Monge I

13. Are you interested in researching?

Yes NO

14. Motivates you to carry out research despite the impediments that it may have

Yes NO

15. When do you carry out research activities as you like to work?

Only Team up he is indifferent

16. If you answered that you like to work in a team, with which of the following roles do you feel most identified?

As project leader as a member of the technical team Other which: _____

17. Have you received any awards for your research work?

Yes NO

18. Have you received any recognition for your research work?

Yes NO

19. Are you satisfied with your investigative work?

Yes NO

20. Do you consider that the economic situation is an impediment to carry out research?

Yes NO

21. Do you consider that family burden is an impediment to carry out research?

Yes NO

22. Do you consider that the workload is an impediment to carrying out research?

Yes NO

SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION

23. In the last 7 years you have published a scientific article in indexed journals

Yes NO

24. How many articles have you published in the last 7 years in indexed databases?:

25. Number of publications in the last 7 years in open-access journals (open access) ____

26. Number of publications in the last 7 years in the Scopus database: _____

27. Number of publications in the last 7 years in the WOS database: _____

28. Number of publications in the last 7 years in the Scielo database: _____

29. Number of publications in the last 7 years in the Latindex database: _____

30. Does it have h-index?

Yes NO You don't know what the h index is

31. If it has index h, what is its number? _____

ACADEMIC FACTORS

32. Do you have postgraduate studies?

Yes NO

33. Select which Postgraduate studies you have (*you can select several options*)

Master degree Master's degree Doctor's Degree PhD Graduate Postdoc
Specialty. Which _____

34. Select your groin compression level

Essential Intermediate Advanced None

35. In your research, how do you carry out the bibliographic search?

I entrust it to third parties use google use google academic uses
databases Other. Which: _____

36. If you answered that you use databases, select which ones you use for your search? (*you can select several options*)

PUBMED SCHINAL SCOPUS MEDLINE SCIELO EBSCO
REDALYC LATINDEXT UP TODAY WEB OF SCIENCE VLEX
OTHER. WHICH _____

37. Do you use bibliographic reference managers as a research support tool?

Yes NO you don't know them

38. If your answer is affirmative, which ones do you use most frequently?

end note Mendely Zotero Citeulike PROCITE
ReferenceManager RefWorks Other

Specify:

39. Do you use any type of Statistical Software?

Yes NO you don't know them

40. Select which statistical software you use most frequently in your research? (*you can select several options*)

SPSS Stata minitab R statgraphics atlas you Ethnography
 Nlive Nlive SAS
 Other (specify:

41. In your research, who performs the statistical analysis?

You other researcher hire others

42. Do you currently have a subscription to any Scientific journal?

Yes NO

43. If your answer was positive, to which magazine do you have a subscription? _____

44. Are you currently a member of any Scientific Society?

Yes No, which: _____

45. If your answer was positive, to which Scientific Society do you belong? _____

46. Do you belong to any research group?

Yes NO

47. Do you lead any research group?

Yes NO

48. In the last year have you participated in any research?

Yes NO

49. doHow many investigations have you participated in? _____

50. doHave you attended research methodology training in the last 2 years?

Yes NO

51. How many trainings have you attended in the last year? _____

52. Have you participated as a thesis advisor?

Yes NO

53. In the last year, how many theses have you advised: _____

54. Educational levels in which he has been a thesis advisor(*you can select several options*)

Master degree Master's degree Doctor's Degree PhD Graduate Postdoc
Specialty.

LABOR FACTORS

55. Do you have facilities to carry out research activities in your work?

Yes NO

56. Does the university provide you time in the week to carry out research activities?

YES NO

57. If yes, how many hours a week do you have to do research? _____

58. Has your boss encouraged you to do research?

Yes NO

59. Have you received any research training from the university in the last year?

Yes NO

60. Have you received any research funding from the university?

Yes NO

61. Have you received any incentive from the university for publishing a scientific article in indexed databases?

Yes NO

62. Do you consider that the university has the physical infrastructure to carry out research (Laboratories, equipment, etc.)?

Yes NO

63. Do you consider that the university has the technological infrastructure to carry out research (computer equipment, software, simulators)?

Yes NO

64. Do you consider that the university has the documentary infrastructure to carry out research (Library)?

Yes NO

65. Have you received support from the university for the formulation and execution of research projects?

Yes NO

66. Have you received any kind of research funding from the university?

Yes NO

67. Do you consider that the university provides facilities for the development of research with external financing?

Yes NO

68. Does the university promote internships at national research centers?

Yes NO

69. Does the university promote internships in international research centers?

Yes NO

70. Does the university support you in the translation required for the acceptance of scientific articles in journals in English?

Yes NO

71. Are the investigations carried out at the university framed within the lines of research established by CONCYTEC?

Yes NO

72. Is the research carried out at the university framed within the institutional lines of research?

Yes NO

73. Does the institution have a Research Ethics Committee?

Yes NO

74. Is it normalized?

Yes NO Does not know

75. If it is normalized, what teaching category are you in?

Assistant Associated Major

76. Time dedicated to the University (weekly hours): _____

77. Type of employment contract

Part time Full time Other . Which _____

78. Teaching Hours: _____

79. Non-teaching hours: _____

80. Hours dedicated to research: _____